

Study on Powder Electrode Potentials

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Special types of electrodes, termed powder electrodes by W. Tomassi¹, have been used for measurement of potentials. The powders used were barium sulphate and copper oxide of different grades and sizes. The conditions under which steady values of potentials are obtained have been investigated and reasons for acquirement of steady potentials suggested.

Valuable information regarding physicochemical characteristics of varied systems have been obtained in many instances from potential measurements. Very often, the electrodes chosen for specific purposes have been of the reversible type, thus permitting the use of Nernst's relation for the evaluation of potential magnitude. In 1950's Tomassi and coworkers²⁻⁵ carried out series of investigations into the nature of surface of insoluble solid powders as revealed by kinetic and adsorption experiments and tried to correlate these kinetic and adsorption properties with the potentials of an (irreversible) electrode containing the solid as a powder phase.

To be more specific, two types of powder electrodes have been defined and described in literature⁶. The powder electrode of the first kind consists of a leading out Pt-wire coated with a metal. This metal-sheathed platinum is dipped into a solution containing metal ions and is surrounded by fine metal powder or drillings. Evidently, such an electrode would function reversibly and it is so found in practice, although very slight (sometimes insignificant) departures⁶ from Nernst value have been observed. These departures are suspected to be caused by the presence of powder phase. The compound powder electrodes of the second kind are simpler in construction and peculiar in behaviour. It consists of simple platinum wire dipping in a solution of a reference electrolyte e.g., KCl of definite normality, the leading out Pt-wire being surrounded by a suitable powder (such as barium sulphate or copper oxide in the present investigation) inside the solution. This electrode is coupled with a reference half cell, calomel electrode, for potential investigation. A diagrammatic sketch of such an electrode assembly appears in figure 1.

The electrode, so constructed, is expected to yield widely fluctuating potentials. It is well known that Pt-wire dipped in an aqueous solution gives very erratic potential values—fluctuations are caused sometimes even by movement of the wire from one disposition to

1. W. Tomassi, A. Fręckiewicz and M. Sanchez, *Przemysl. Chemi.*, 1955, **11**, 492.
2. W. Tomassi, *Przemysl. Chemi.*, 1959, **38**, 285.
3. W. Tomassi and M. Prokopowicz, *Przemysl. Chemi.*, 1958, **37**, 465.
4. W. Tomassi, H. Jankowska and M. Prokopowicz, *Przemysl. Chemi.*, 1957, **13**, 683.
5. W. Tomassi and J. Bulawa, *Przemysl. Chemi.*, 1959, **38**, 544.
6. *Advances in Chemical Physics* (Vol. III), Edited by I. Prigogine. Interscience Publishers, 1961, p. 239.

another during any set of measurements. The existence of a powder phase completely surrounding the Pt-wire, preconditioned by prolonged contact with the powder and the indifferent electrolyte, causes the powder electrode to register a more or less steady potential.

Fig. I.

1. Powder phase. 2. Platinum contact. 3. Test tube A of length 8 cm. and diameter 1 cm. 4. Hole in the wall of test tube. 5. Beaker containing reference electrolyte. 6. Salt bridge to saturated calomel.

EXPERIMENTAL

A sample, Gr. I, of barium sulphate was prepared⁷ in the laboratory by reaction of barium chloride with sulphuric acid, followed by digestion and purification after washing it free from chloride and acid. Gr. I was then dried at 100–110° and next allowed to age for a month. Another stock of barium sulphate (E. Merck-extra pure) powder was divided into three lots. The first portion, termed hereafter as Gr. II., was used in the experiments without any further treatment. The second and the third lots were heated to 300° and 700° and kept at the respective temperatures for 5 to 6 hours. Each lot, after heating, was allowed to age for one month before use in potential measurements. These two separate lots will be described as Gr. III and Gr. IV respectively. It is presumed that these four lots would have somewhat, at least, different surface characteristics.

A new lot of BaSO₄ (E. Merck-extra pure) will be designated as Gr. IIA. The specific conductances of the suspensions, each containing 0.1 gm. of the sample in 50 ml. of conductivity water of pH 6.7 are recorded below :

	Sp. cond.	Temp. = 29°
Gr. I	=	1.11 × 10 ⁻⁵ ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
Gr. II	=	1.822 × 10 ⁻⁵ ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
Gr. III	=	1.588 × 10 ⁻⁵ ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
Gr. IV	=	1.333 × 10 ⁻⁵ ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
Cond. water	=	0.78 × 10 ⁻⁵ ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹

7. Analytical Chemistry (Vol. II), F. P. Treadwell and T. Hall., John Wiley and Sons Inc., 1958, p. 393.

For potential measurement, 1 gm. of BaSO_4 (Gr. I) was taken in the tube A, the latter being placed in a 100 ml. pyrex beaker containing 50 ml. of 1 *N* KCl solution which was in contact with the powder through a communicating hole in the glass tube. A glass tube with a sealed-in platinum wire, previously cleansed and heated in a flame after moistening in alcohol, was thrust inside the Gr. I powder, so that the latter completely encompassed the entire protruding portion of the platinum wire about 1 cm. in length. While inserting the platinum wire in the powder, care was taken to avoid imprisonment of air bubbles in between the platinum surface and powder and also within the bulk of the powder phase, by gently agitating the powder mass under the surface of solution with a thin glass rod. It was allowed to stand in this condition for a period of 16 to 20 hrs to attain equilibrium. At the end of that period the assembly, consisting of the beaker with the normal KCl solution and the tube with its feed suspended in the beaker, was coupled with a saturated calomel electrode.

The same procedure was followed for Gr. II, Gr. IIA, Gr. III and Gr. IV BaSO_4 powders before potential measurements were made. (In some cases a 16 hour equilibrium period was insufficient for attainment of a steady potential value. In such instances, readings were intermittently taken till more or less steady values were recorded). The values obtained with BaSO_4 powder electrodes, using Gr. I, II, IIA, III and IV as the powder phase, in contact with different concentrations of potassium chloride are recorded in Table I. During the period when the measurements were taken, temperatures varied from 25° to 35°.

Separate experiments indicated very small values of temperature coefficients of e.m.f. and hence all measurements were made at the prevailing room temperatures. The temperature varied over a range 25° to 35° during the entire session of measurements and repetition experiments.

TABLE I

Effect of concn. of reference electrolyte on powder electrode potentials
Average temperature = 30°. Saturated Calomel electrode = Negative.

Grade of BaSO_4	Cell voltage in volts with reference electrolyte			
	1.0NKCl	0.1NKCl	0.01NKCl	0.001NKCl
Gr. I	0.275	0.280	0.305	×
Gr. IIA	0.220	0.224	0.231	0.272
Gr. II	0.135	0.141	0.164	0.172
Gr. III	0.075	0.077	0.080	0.085
Gr. IV	0.027	0.029	0.029	0.030

Any possible effect on powder potential due to one or the other of the following enlisted factors was also additionally investigated.

- Use of powder (viz.— BaSO_4) from separate preparations.
- The degree of packing.
- The quantity of powder used.
- Length of Pt-wire used as electrode.
- Extent of immersion of the Pt-wire.

(a) In the foregoing Table, Gr. I represents BaSO_4 powders prepared in the laboratory under conditions already stated where as Gr. IIA and Gr. II stand for E. Merck extra pure products of two different lots. The potential data suggest that even with the same compound, the potentials vary due to the possible differences that must exist in the surface natures of the powder of three different preparations.

(b) and (c). The effect of degree of packing of the powder phase in the tube A (Fig. 1) and also of the quantity of powder on potential magnitudes was tested by experimenting with a number of systems. Only one sample data table, out of many drawn up, is presented below :

TABLE II

Powder Phase Gr. II BaSO_4 . Ref. electrolyte 1N KCl.

Calomel (saturated) = Negative pole.

After 20 hrs. equilibration period cell voltage recorded in volts.

Average Temp. = 30°

I	II	Time of Reading					
		III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII
No. of sets	Initial reading after equilbm.	1 hr.	2 hrs.	2½ hrs.	3 hrs.	3½ hrs.	4 hrs.
A	.134	.134	.134	.134	.134	.121	.105
B	.137	.138	.137	.137	.137	.126	.095
C	.138	.136	.134	.134	.135	.123	.110
D	.135	.141	.138	.138	.135	.129	.081
E	.141	.144	.141	.142	.141	.145	.092

The row marked A was obtained by using 1 gm. powder, the rows B and C with 2 and 3 gms. of BaSO_4 powder respectively. In all these three, the powders were allowed to settle naturally around the platinum electrodes. The rows marked D and E, were obtained with 2 grams of powders each and a more or less compact settling was effected by centrifuging. After the constancy of the reading was ensured as indicated in column IV the powders in all the electrode tubes were stirred so as to loosen the packing and readings taken. these are recorded at timings given in columns V and VI. The almost steady values of the readings irrespective of the amounts as well as degree of packing (very slight increase in the case of D and E) are evident from the table.

The readings within the two vertical lines, under the time headings of columns VII and VIII, represent situations with the Pt-wire drawn out of the powder phase and suspended in KCl solution of 1N concentration above the powder bulk. The sharp departure of the potential values with no fixity of magnitude in different cases is in evidence. The corresponding data are incorporated merely to emphasise the fact, that the platinum wire, unless surrounded by powder, would show widely varying potentials.

(d) The length of the Pt-wire used as electrode and embedded in the powder mass was varied from 0.5 cm to 3 cm in many check tests and it was found to have little influence on the potential magnitudes.

(e) The complete immersion of the Pt-wire inside the powder is a necessity for steady values of potentials. Out of the data compiled on this aspect, a representative table is given with the actual timings. The last two columns of Table II will also bear out this point.

TABLE III

Average temperature = 30°. Equilibration period 16 hrs. to 20 hrs.

Calomel electrode (saturated) = Negative.

Powder Phase Gr. II BaSO₄, Reference electrolyte KCl 1N.

Time of obs.	A					B					C			
	11-00 a.m.	11-30 a.m.	12-00 noon	12-35 p.m.	1-00 p.m.	1-35 p.m.	2-00 p.m.	2-30 p.m.	3-00 p.m.	3-35 p.m.	4-00 p.m.	4-50 p.m.	5-30 p.m.	6-00 p.m.
Cell voltage (volts.)	.185	.182	.180	.165	.177	.164	.185	.184	.185	.200	.190	.200	.134	.132

The readings under A were taken with Pt-contact electrode half immersed in powder phase and the other half in the reference solution above the powder phase. Those under B indicate measurements with the Pt-wire entirely pulled out of the powder phase and resting in the solution. The last column represents the situation with the contact electrode completely immersed in the powder bulk. The value reached in the last instance (0.134 v) is very close to the figure viz., 0.135 v. for the same powder and reference electrolyte as recorded in Table I.

The effects of varying concentrations of different electrolytes, ranging from types having common ions with the powder phase, such as BaCl₂ and K₂SO₄, to ones with high adsorbability e.g., HCl and KOH, were studied. The results of measurements are collected in Table IV.

Similar series of experiments with pure copper oxide (guaranteed reagent quality) of different mesh sizes were used as powder phase in electrode potential measurements. Reference electrolytes, used in two sets of measurements, were KCl in one instance and copper sulphate in the other. One electrode of the assembly was saturated calomel electrode as usual. The potential values recorded by the leadingout Pt-wire dipping fully in the powder phase registered more or less steady values after suitable equilibration period and tended to fluctuate as soon as the Pt-wire was half or fully drawn out of the powder phase. The potential values varied with grain sizes of the powder and the effects of different concentrations of KCl as well as other electrolytes were manifested as in the barium sulphate case. Specific data are not given here.

Since in the potential measurements, BaSO₄ powder and the reference electrolyte KCl were used, separate experiments were made to ascertain the extent of adsorption of KCl by BaSO₄ by following titrimetric methods. The results indicated only trace or negligible adsorption.

TABLE IV

Saturated Calomel Electrode negative pole.

Average Temp. -30°

Equilibration period 20 hrs.

Grades of BaSO ₄ in Powder electrode	Cell Potential in Volts					Remarks
	N.KCl.	N.KCl. 1M BaCl ₂	N.KCl. 01M BaCl ₂	N.KCl. .001M BaCl ₂	N.KCl.	
Gr I	0.275	0.302	0.285	×		Names of electrolytes in contact with the powder electrodes are given at the heads of the columns.
Gr. II	0.135	0.248	0.225	0.220		
Gr. III	0.075	0.156	0.125	0.104		
Gr. IV	0.027	0.115	0.083	0.070		
	N KCl	N KCl	N KCl	N KCl	N KCl	
	0.1 N HCl	.01 N HCl	.001 N HCl	.0005 N HCl	.0002 N HCl	
Gr. II	0.448	0.380	0.225	0.150	0.135	
Gr. III	0.620	0.540	0.127	0.080	0.078	
	N KCl	N KCl	N KCl	N KCl	N KCl	N KCl
	.001N	.002N	.004N	.02N	0.1N	0.2N
	KOH	KOH	KOH	KOH	KOH	KOH
Gr. II	0.0755	0.035	0.013	0.135*	0.030*	0.075*
	N KCl, 0.5 N K ₂ SO ₄			N KCl, 0.025 N K ₂ SO ₄		
Gr. II	0.142			0.133		
Gr. III	0.072			0.072		

* Polarity changes.

DISCUSSION

A complete interpretation of the development of steady potential at the powder phase electrode seems to be lacking. Platinum serves as a very badly reversible oxygen electrode and in the absence of a continuous and regular bubbling of H₂-gas does not serve as a good H₂-electrode either. That the powder electrode potential cannot be identified with any Nernst type potential is evident from the following :

(i) The potentials obtained with the same compound as the powder phase prepared under different conditions are different; this is also true for the same powder subjected to different heat treatments (Table I).

(ii) The potential values measured with different concentrations of added electrolytes (Table IV) do not increase or decrease by amounts as might be expected from an equation of the Nernst type.

Tomassi *et al.*⁶, have ascribed the powder potential to a combination of several phase-boundary potentials viz., potentials existing at the (i) Pt-solution interface, (ii) powder-solution interface, (iii) Pt-powder interface. The net overall potential, according to them, satisfies an equation of the type

$$\pi = aT^b$$

where, π -powder potential; T -surface concentration and a and b are constants.

While the great effect of adsorption and hence, of the surface on the powder potential can hardly be doubted, the attribution of any part of the overall potential to the Pt-powder interface seems a superfluity. One can always imagine a layer of solution separating the Pt-surface from the powder grains, however, tightly the latter be packed. We suppose that the erratic potential values of a bare Pt-wire dipped in KCl solution are due to variable and fluctuating amounts of adsorption of ions on the Pt-surface. The presence of a mantle of powder grains (BaSO_4) in KCl solution creates a zone (comprising the powder and the entrapped solution) of definite chloride ion activity surrounded by bulk solution of KCl of different chloride ion activity. This creation of new activity region is connected with the adsorbability of ions on the powder grains and the formation of accompanying double layer of opposite ions and is verified experimentally by measuring the distinct potential difference arising between two Ag/AgCl electrodes, one resting inside the powder phase and the other in the bulk KCl solution. The double layers associated with each powder grain control the overall movements of the ions of the solution inside the powder mass and thus largely restrict the flexibility and fluctuation of the amounts of adsorption of ions on the Pt-surface. The latter, therefore, registers a steady potential value.

The partial exposure of any part of the Pt-wire to the bulk of the solution tends to cause variable adsorption of ions on the exposed segment thus causing fluctuation in potential values (Tables II and III). It thus turns out that the nature of the compound and of the surface, which determines ion adsorbability, determines the nature of double layer. The latter, in turn, controls the type and amount of adsorption ion and hence of potential of the Pt-wire.

The negligible adsorption by BaSO_4 as observed experimentally *vis-a-vis* the role of adsorbability of ions and setting up of double layer round each grain of BaSO_4 as a means for explaining the constancy of powder electrode potential are not mutually contradictory. The extent of adsorption necessary for fixing the nature of a double layer may be on a microscopic level and need not be in macroscopic amounts determinable by ordinary adsorption experiments.

Phenomenologically, the passage of charge from the Pt-wire, towards the bulk of the solution or *vice versa* may be deemed as a traversal of a region of irregular three dimensional array of potential wells created by double layers associated with the adjacent particles constituting the powder phase.